

ELIXIR Data and Interoperability Platforms 2023 Face-to-Face Event Summary Report

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Background

ELIXIR, the European research infrastructure for life science data, has five Platforms focused on technical activities - these are Data, Compute, Interoperability, Tools and Training. The ELIXIR Data and Interoperability Platforms held their third joint meeting last year on the 21-23 November 2023. The Face-to-Face meeting was hosted at the Novotel Hotel Schiphol Airport, Amsterdam, Netherlands. This annual meeting brought together members of the two Platforms in order to begin work on their respective project plans by convening individual work package (WP) teams, and to facilitate broader cross-Platform strategy planning for the coming year and the new 2024-2028 ELIXIR Programme.

Event format and content

The Data and Interoperability Face-to-Face event ran over three days in a fully hybrid format. The event included topic-focussed sessions, smaller group breakouts for the individual Platform WP teams and additional satellite sessions to create space for important conversations.

The WP breakout sessions ran throughout the event and acted as a form of kick-off for the new ELIXIR Programme, giving time for WP members to get to know one another and become familiar with the content of their WPs. A key focus of each breakout was to understand what the first period of work would entail, and begin defining the finer details of their work plan activities.

Topic-focussed sessions of the event covered the following areas:

- The ELIXIR Communities session incorporated flash talks from members of the Systems Biology, Rare Disease, and Food & Nutrition Communities and was followed by a panel discussion on the links between ELIXIR Communities and the Data and Interoperability Platforms.
- The sustainability workshop featured a presentation from Josh Young of Phoenix Bioinformatics, which sustains a number of bioinformatics resources such as the Arabidopsis Information Resource and CyVerse. It has developed and deployed various funding models, and Josh discussed the different advantages and disadvantages of the common mechanisms for achieving financial sustainability as a bioinformatics resource.
- An EC funding workshop was held, during which participants had the opportunity to put together their own response to a funding call using a provided template. This helped foster strategic thinking for future EC proposals and how to incorporate elements and people from the Data & Interoperability Platforms in any potential bids.
- Finally, a session on the future of Open, Research Data Management, and FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) featured presentations from the Research Data Management Community, and a talk about FAIR in structural biology computational workflows and led to some vibrant discussions about the original purpose of the FAIR principles and how those have evolved over time.

The final day of the event hosted a satellite session for the ELIXIR Core Data Resources Forum:

- Roxanne Wyns from KU Leuven provided an overview of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Long Term Data Preservation Task Force recommendations for data preservation. A useful consideration for biodata resources focused on aligning to EOSC's recommendations.
- The recently launched Global Open Research Commons (GORC) model version 1 was presented by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE). GORC provides a framework for a global trusted ecosystem that provides seamless access to high quality interoperable research outputs and services, which can be applied in the context of biodata resources.
- Renato Juacaba Neto (EMBL-EBI) presented highlights from the FAIR Impact & FAIRCORE4EOSC projects supporting FAIR data outputs.
- The standardised metrics monitoring framework developed by Project COUNTER was presented by Tasha Mellins-Cohen (COUNTER). This metrics framework is a useful step towards standardising the difficult landscape of biodata resource metric collection and analysis.
- Finally, the session closed with discussion on the developing idea of the Community Databases accreditation concept. A key outcome was commitment from the Data Platform members to submit a workshop proposal to the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting to discuss the concept further with a broader group of stakeholders.

Significant event outcomes

- Data and Interoperability Platform members had the chance to meet one another in person and build strong foundations for the start of the 2024-2028 ELIXIR Programme.
- Work package members mapped out their early priorities and actionable steps to start work on their milestones and deliverables.
- Community and Platform members forged new connections and identified areas of overlapping interest.
- Participants were exposed to new ways of thinking about sustainability of open life science resources.
- Attendees learnt how to conceptualise a successful EC funding proposal.
- Vibrant discussion of the FAIR principles led to a new understanding of their origins and ideas about their future.
- New perspectives were shared about how FAIR applies not just to data, but also to workflows and infrastructure.
- Core Data Resource stakeholders were engaged in discussion across a broad range of important topics including EOSC, metric and impact monitoring, FAIR enabling projects and initiative outputs, Community Databases and data preservation recommendations.

Participant feedback on the event

Participant feedback generally paints a very positive picture. Participants found the parallel breakout sessions for individual Work Package teams to be highly valuable (11 out of 13 agreed or strongly agreed), with a similar sentiment towards the smaller group format of the breakout sessions themselves (11 out of 13 agreed or strongly agreed). Overall, sessions were effective in their goal of creating a positive feeling from attendees towards their individual team (12 out of 13 agreed or strongly agreed).

Somewhat expectedly, there were mixed opinions regarding the parallel scheduling of sessions. While 8 out of 12 attendees agreed or strongly agreed that the main room sessions were useful, several comments highlighted issues with them running concurrently with breakout sessions. Some suggestions included avoiding concurrent sessions altogether or extending the conference by a day to accommodate all desired content.

The survey also indicated that attendees who participated virtually did so primarily due to general travel constraints or family and caring responsibilities, not due to health and safety concerns. Those who did attend in-person cited the in-person experience, the networking and collaboration opportunities and the Work Package team-building exercises as important factors in their decision. This, together with more than twice as many attendees registered for virtual attendance as in-person, shows the importance of running all meetings and sessions in full hybrid format to maximise the inclusivity of Platform events.

Conclusion

The Data and Interoperability Platforms hosted another successful joint face-to-face event during 2023. Significant progress was made in launching both Platform project plans for 2024-2026 and members discussed a diverse range of key topics such as leveraging EC funding, engaging ELIXIR Communities, and resource sustainability.

